

ON CONTINUUM APPROXIMATION IN STABILITY THEORY OF NON-LINEAR COMPOSITES UNDERGOING LARGE DEFORMATIONS

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SUMMARY: The investigation is devoted to substantiation of the continuum theory of internal instability applied to predict fracture of composites under uniaxial compression. Based on the results obtained within the scope of the model of piecewise-homogeneous medium and three-dimensional linearised theory of deformable bodies stability (TLTDBS), the accuracy of the continuum theory is examined for laminated incompressible materials undergoing large deformations. Estimation of the accuracy of the continuum theory is illustrated by numerical results for the particular models of composites when the layers are hyperelastic materials with the elastic potential of the neo-Hookean type (Treloar's potential). At that the influence of the layers' thickness and their stiffness on the accuracy of the continuum theory is determined.

KEYWORDS: laminated composites, internal instability, compressive fracture, model of piecewise-homogeneous medium, continuum theory, non-linear material, large deformations, neo-Hookean hyperelastic material.

INTRODUCTION

The wide usage of the continuum theory in mechanics, due to its simplicity, puts into consideration the question of its accuracy and of its domain of applicability. The answer may be given only by comparison of the results delivered by both the continuum theory and the most accurate approach (i.e. the piecewise-homogeneous medium model). Indeed, the approach based on the model of piecewise-homogeneous medium (Fig. 1), where the behaviour of each material component is described by three-dimensional equations of solid mechanics, enables to investigate the material mechanical response in the most rigorous way at microscopic level (exact solution). However, due to its complexity, this method is restricted to a very small group of problems. This makes the continuum theory (Fig. 2) more attractive since it involves significant simplifications: the composite is modelled as a homogeneous anisotropic solid with effective material constants, by means of which physical properties of the original material, shape and volume fraction of the constituents are taken into account. The continuum theory may be applied when the scale of the investigated phenomenon (for example, the wavelength of the mode of stability loss l) is considerably larger than that of a

material structure (say, the fibre diameter or layer thickness h), i.e. $l \gg h$. The method based on the model of the piecewise-homogeneous medium is free from such restrictions. It is, therefore, the most accurate one and has a much larger domain of applicability than the continuum theory. The results obtained by the continuum theory must follow from those derived using the model of piecewise-homogeneous medium when the ratio of the scale of phenomena and the scale of structure tends to zero, i.e. when $hl^{-1} \rightarrow 0$. If this is the case, the continuum theory can be considered as asymptotically accurate one.

Table I: A schematic of the approaches

Fig. 1: Model of piecewise-homogeneous medium

Fig. 2: Continuum theory

The schematic of the approaches as applied to the problem on instability (microbuckling) in compression of laminated composites is given in Table I. Except the exact approaches, which based on the three-dimensional linearised theory of deformable bodies stability (TLTDBS) (expounded, for instance, in [2]), there are also approximate approaches to the considered problem proposed in [3] and by many other authors. Detailed reviews on these approximate approaches are given, for example, in [6, 7]. However, the approximate approaches proved to be not worth applying [1]. This is discussed in some detail in the next section.

At present, investigations of the continuum theory accuracy in relation to the model of piecewise homogeneous medium have been done only for other physical phenomena – for example, for the problems of wave propagation [8, 9]. But, there are not yet such investigations for problems on stability loss in composite structures undergoing finite (large) deformations. This paper fills the gap. It is devoted to substantiation of the continuum theory [1] applied to predict fracture of a laminated composite material with a periodical structure undergoing large deformations in uniaxial compression. (Within the scope of this theory the moment of stability loss in the structure of the material – internal instability according to Biot [10] – is treated as the beginning of the fracture process.) Special attention is paid to calculation of the continuum theory accuracy for the particular laminated composites consisting of hyperelastic materials, taking into account the influence of geometrical and mechanical properties of the individual layers.

INSTABILITY (MICROBUCKLING) OF COMPOSITES UNDER LARGE DEFORMATIONS

On the Applicability of the Approximate Approach

The approximate approaches (Table I) do not describe the phenomenon under consideration even on the qualitative level. They proved [1, 11] to give a huge discrepancy in comparison with the exact approach and with experimental data. For example, even for the simplest case of all linear elastic compressible layers of a composite undergoing small precritical deformations and considered within the scope of geometrically linear theory, Rosen's formulae [3] for the shear and extension modes are not worth applying. Indeed, Rosen's model may give not only critical strains which are significantly higher than those obtained by the exact approach but sometimes predicts even the mode of stability loss, different from that obtained within the exact approach. Moreover, as it was shown in [1], even the continuum theory based on equations of TLTDDBS [2] (i.e. based on exact approach) gives much better results than Rosen's approach. Indeed, critical strains predicted by the Rosen's formulae for the shear mode are always higher than those predicted by the continuum theory [1]; and for small volume fractions of matrix the approximate approach gives just physically unrealistic strength limits. It is not a surprise. In spite of using the model of piecewise-homogeneous medium, Rosen's approach involves considerable simplifications, namely, modelling of the stiff layers by the thin beam theory and the one-dimensional model for the matrix. It makes the results of this approach inaccurate even for simple cases. For more complicated models which take into account large deformations and geometrical and physical non-linearity (e.g. those considered in this paper) the approximate approach is definitely inapplicable and one can expect even bigger difference between the exact and approximate approaches.

Problem Statement within the Scope of the Piecewise-Homogeneous Medium Model

Let us consider briefly the statement of the stability problem (microbuckling) for composites undergoing large deformations. Let composite consists of alternating layers with thicknesses $2h_r$ and $2h_m$ (Fig. 3), which are simulated by incompressible non-linear elastic isotropic or orthotropic solids with general form of constitutive equations. The material is uniaxially compressed in the plane of layers by “dead” loads applied at infinity in such a manner that equal deformations along all layers are provided and, therefore, the plain strain problem should be considered. Since the analysis in this paper is based on the general approach developed in [1, 2], some equations derived earlier are given below for clarity sake.

Fig. 3: The co-ordinate system and applied loads (uniform uniaxial compression)

Within the scope of the most accurate approach (i.e. using the model of piecewise-homogeneous medium and equations of TLTDBS) we have to solve the following eigen-value problem. Henceforth all values corresponding to the precritical state will be marked by the superscript '0' to distinguish them from perturbations of the same values. Indices r and m show that the value is relevant to fibre or matrix, respectively. The axial displacement and strain (in terms of the elongation factor λ_j in the direction of axis OX_j) for the considered type of loading is

$$u_i^0 = (\lambda_i - 1)x_i, \quad \lambda_i = const, \quad \varepsilon_{ij}^0 = (\lambda_i - 1)\delta_{ij}, \quad \text{where } \delta_{ij} \text{ is Kronecker symbol} \quad (1)$$

The stability equations for the individual layers are

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} t_{ij}^r = 0, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} t_{ij}^m = 0 \quad (2)$$

Non-symmetrical stress tensor t_{ij} is referred to the unit area of the relevant surface elements in the undeformed state (in the reference configuration). Namely, t_{ij} is a stress component acting in direction of OX_j at the elementary area with normal OX_i . This is non-symmetrical Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor or nominal stress tensor using the terminology of Hill [12]. Further we shall consider also the symmetrical stress tensor S_{ij} which reduces to σ_{ij} for the case of small precritical deformations. For incompressible solids stresses are connected with displacements as (p is hydrostatic pressure)

$$t_{ij} = \kappa_{ij\alpha\beta} \frac{\partial u_\alpha}{\partial x_\beta} + \delta_{ij} q_j p, \quad q_i = \lambda_i^{-1} \quad \text{with the incompressibility condition } \lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3 = 1 \quad (3)$$

Components of tensor κ depend on material properties and on loads (i.e. on precritical state). The quantity characterising the precritical state, i.e. stress S_{ij}^0 or strain ε_{ij}^0 , is the parameter in respect to which the eigen-value problem should be solved. In the most general case

$$\kappa_{ij\alpha\beta} = \lambda_j \lambda_\alpha [\delta_{ij} \delta_{\alpha\beta} A_{\beta i} + (1 - \delta_{ij})(\delta_{i\alpha} \delta_{j\beta} \mu_{ij} + \delta_{i\beta} \delta_{j\alpha} \mu_{ji})] + \delta_{i\beta} \delta_{j\alpha} S_{\beta\beta}^0 \quad (4)$$

The particular expressions for $\kappa_{ij\alpha\beta}$ for numerous kinds of constitutive equations were obtained in [2]. For hyperelastic solids, if Φ is the strain energy density function (elastic potential),

$$A_{\beta i} = A_{\beta i}(\Phi, \varepsilon_{nl}^0), \quad \mu_{\beta i} = \mu_{\beta i}(\Phi, \varepsilon_{nl}^0) \quad (5)$$

To complete the problem statement, the boundary conditions should be written for each individual interface

$$t_{22}^r = t_{22}^m, \quad t_{12}^r = t_{12}^m, \quad u_2^r = u_2^m, \quad u_1^r = u_1^m \quad (6)$$

The detailed problem statement and solutions within the scope of the most accurate approach (as applied to axisymmetrical and non-axisymmetrical modes, biaxial and uniaxial compression) were given previously for the above materials in [4, 11].

ANALYSIS OF SOLUTIONS OBTAINED BY THE MODEL OF PIECEWISE-HOMOGENEOUS MEDIUM

Limit Transition to the Long-Wave Asymptotic

To perform the asymptotic analysis we should apply the condition of applicability of the continuum theory (i.e. $hl^{-1} \rightarrow 0$) to all formulae and calculate the limits analytically under this condition, which yields

$$\alpha_r \rightarrow 0, \quad \alpha_m \rightarrow 0, \quad \text{where } \alpha_r = \pi h_r l^{-1}, \quad \alpha_m = \pi h_m l^{-1}$$

$$\cosh \alpha_r \eta_j^r \rightarrow 1, \quad \cosh \alpha_m \eta_j^m \rightarrow 1, \quad \sinh \alpha_r \eta_j^r \rightarrow \alpha_r \eta_j^r, \quad \sinh \alpha_m \eta_j^m \rightarrow \alpha_m \eta_j^m, \quad j = 2, 3 \quad (7)$$

In Eqn 7, l is half-wave length of modes of stability loss along the OX_1 axis. As a result of such manipulations we can obtain the long-wave approximation (if $\alpha \rightarrow 0$ then $l \rightarrow \infty$). Characteristic determinants were derived earlier [4, 11] by the most accurate approach (i.e. within the model of piecewise-homogeneous medium) for four modes of stability loss. On substitution of Eqn 7 into those characteristic determinants we find, after a number of rearrangements, that in the case of uniaxial compression (the plane problem) the characteristic equations for the 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th modes of stability loss are, respectively,

$$\frac{(\eta_2^{r^2} - \eta_3^{r^2})(\eta_2^{m^2} - \eta_3^{m^2})\pi^2}{l^2 \lambda_1^2} \left[\frac{h_m}{h_r} (\kappa_{1212}^m - \kappa_{1212}^r)^2 - \left(\frac{h_m}{h_r} \kappa_{1221}^m + \kappa_{1221}^r \right) \left(\kappa_{2112}^m + \frac{h_m}{h_r} \kappa_{2112}^r \right) \right] = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$(\eta_2^{r^2} - \eta_3^{r^2})(\eta_2^{m^2} - \eta_3^{m^2})\eta_2^m \eta_3^m \lambda_1^2 \kappa_{2112}^m \kappa_{2112}^r = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$(\eta_2^{r^2} - \eta_3^{r^2})(\eta_2^{m^2} - \eta_3^{m^2})\eta_2^r \eta_3^r \eta_2^m \eta_3^m \frac{\pi^2}{l^2} \lambda_1^2 \kappa_{2112}^m \kappa_{2112}^r \left(\frac{h_m}{h_r} + 1 \right) = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$(\eta_2^{r^2} - \eta_3^{r^2})(\eta_2^{m^2} - \eta_3^{m^2})\eta_2^r \eta_3^r \lambda_1^2 \kappa_{2112}^m \kappa_{2112}^r = 0 \quad (11)$$

Analysis of Equations for the Particular Modes of Instability

Let us examine the characteristic equations (Eqns 8-11), which correspond now, after the limit transition, to the continuum theory. It was proved that for the considered models of layers the roots of the characteristic equations (i.e. parameters $(\eta_j^r)^2$ and $(\eta_j^m)^2$, which depend on the components of tensor κ and therefore on properties of layers and on loads) are always real and positive. This means, that

$$\text{Re}(\eta_2^r)^2 > 0, \quad \text{Im}(\eta_2^r)^2 = 0, \quad \text{Re}(\eta_2^m)^2 > 0, \quad \text{Im}(\eta_2^m)^2 = 0$$

$$\operatorname{Re}(\eta_3^r)^2 > 0, \quad \operatorname{Im}(\eta_3^r)^2 = 0, \quad \operatorname{Re}(\eta_3^m)^2 > 0, \quad \operatorname{Im}(\eta_3^m)^2 = 0 \quad (12)$$

It is obvious, that the solutions, which correspond to the considered phenomenon of internal instability, must depend on the properties of both alternating layers, i.e. on the ratio h_a/h_m .

Taking into account Eqn 12 one can check that Eqns 9-11, which correspond to the 2nd, 3rd and 4th modes of stability loss, respectively, do not have such solutions and, therefore, do not describe the internal instability in the long-wave approximation. It means also that modes of stability loss, other than the 1st (shear) mode cannot be described by the continuum theory.

Eqn 8, which corresponds to the 1st mode of stability loss (the shear mode according to [3]), generally speaking, may have roots related to the internal instability of the considered materials. This needs a more detailed investigation, which is the next task. For the further analysis components of tensor κ can be expressed [2] as

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_{2112}^r &= \lambda_1^2 \mu_{12}^r, & \kappa_{1221}^r &= \lambda_1^{-2} \mu_{12}^r + (S_{11}^0)^r, & \kappa_{1212}^r &= \mu_{12}^r \\ \kappa_{2112}^m &= \lambda_1^2 \mu_{12}^m, & \kappa_{1221}^m &= \lambda_1^{-2} \mu_{12}^m + (S_{11}^0)^m, & \kappa_{1212}^m &= \mu_{12}^m \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Substituting Eqn 13 into characteristic equation, Eqn 8, for the 1st (shear) mode we derive

$$\frac{h_m}{h_r} (\mu_{12}^r - \mu_{12}^m)^2 - \left[\mu_{12}^r + \frac{h_m}{h_r} \mu_{12}^m + \lambda_1^2 \left((S_{11}^0)^r + \frac{h_m}{h_r} (S_{11}^0)^m \right) \right] \left(\mu_{12}^m + \frac{h_m}{h_r} \mu_{12}^r \right) = 0 \quad (14)$$

In order to analyse Eqn 14, the effective values of stresses and of quantity μ_{12} , denoted respectively as $\langle S_{11}^0 \rangle$ and $\langle \mu_{12} \rangle$, will be utilised. At the moment of stability loss they can be calculated as

$$\langle S_{11}^0 \rangle = (S_{11}^0)^r V_r^* + (S_{11}^0)^m V_m^*, \quad \langle \mu_{12} \rangle = \mu_{12}^r \mu_{12}^m (\mu_{12}^r V_m^* + \mu_{12}^m V_r^*)^{-1} \quad (15)$$

where V_r^* and V_m^* are the volume fractions of the components at the moment of stability loss. At that the volume fractions of the components in the deformed (V_r, V_m) and undeformed states are equal for the same components. Indeed, taking account of Eqn 3 we have

$$V_r^* = \frac{\lambda_2^r h_r}{\lambda_2^r h_r + \lambda_2^m h_m} = \frac{h_r}{h_r + h_m} = V_r, \quad V_m^* = \frac{\lambda_2^m h_m}{\lambda_2^r h_r + \lambda_2^m h_m} = \frac{h_m}{h_r + h_m} = V_m \quad (16)$$

Let us denote the theoretical strength limit as $(\Pi_1^-)_T$. Substituting Eqn 15 and Eqn 16 into Eqn 14, after some rearrangement, we get

$$(\Pi_1^-)_T \equiv -\langle S_{11}^0 \rangle = \lambda_1^{-2} \langle \mu_{12} \rangle \quad (17)$$

This coincides with the results derived within the scope of the continuum theory [1, 2] as applied to non-linear laminated composites undergoing large deformations. Typical critical values of λ_1 are presented in the next section for neo-Hookean materials.

It should be noted that within the scope of the continuum theory Eqn 17 gives the theoretical strength limit for non-linear elastic incompressible composites as a function of $\langle \mu_{12} \rangle$, i.e. the effective value of quantity μ_{12} , which is related to the material properties, Eqn 15. This theoretical strength limit is written for the general form of constitutive equations for layers. If one needs a concrete expression for particular kind of the layers' properties it can be determined using the formulae for μ_{12}^r and μ_{12}^m presented in [1, 2]. For example, for the case of all linear elastic isotropic compressible layers, according to [1], we have $(\Pi_1^-)_r \equiv -\langle \sigma_{11}^0 \rangle = \langle G_{12} \rangle$, where $\langle G_{12} \rangle$ is the effective shear modulus of the laminated composite.

Thus, it is rigorously proved for laminated non-linear elastic composites undergoing large deformations in uniaxial compression that the results of the continuum theory follow as a long-wave approximation from those for the 1st mode of stability loss obtained using the model of piecewise-homogeneous medium. Therefore, the asymptotic accuracy of the continuum theory for such composites is established.

RESULTS FOR HYPERELASTIC NON-LINEAR MATERIALS

Treloar's potential

As an example, let us consider a composite consisting of alternating non-linear elastic isotropic incompressible layers with different properties. Suppose also that materials of these layers are hyperelastic (Eqn 5) and the simplified version of Mooney's potential, namely neo-Hookean potential, may be chosen for their description in the following form

$$\Phi^r = 2C_{10}^r I_1^r(\varepsilon_{ij}^0), \quad \Phi^m = 2C_{10}^m I_1^m(\varepsilon_{ij}^0) \quad (18)$$

where C_{10} is a material constant, and $I_1(\varepsilon)$ is the first algebraic invariant of Cauchy-Green strain tensor. This potential is also called Treloar's potential, after the author who obtained it from an analysis of model of rubber regarded as a system of long molecular interlinking chains [13]. (For transition to the classical linear theory of elasticity under small deformations, we should put $2C_{10} = G$, $G = E/3$, $\nu = 0.5$). Due to the type of applied loads $\lambda_1^r = \lambda_1^m \equiv \lambda_1$. Since the plane strain state is considered in the precritical state, from the condition of incompressibility (Eqn 3) we derive $\lambda_3^r = \lambda_3^m = 1$ and $\lambda_2^r = \lambda_2^m = \lambda_1^{-1}$. Then for uniaxial compression the components of the tensor κ for this model are expressed, according to [2] and Eqns 3-5, as

$$\kappa_{1111} = 2C_{10}(1 + \lambda_1^{-4}), \quad \kappa_{2222} = 4C_{10}, \quad \kappa_{1212} = 2C_{10}\lambda_1^{-2}, \quad \kappa_{1221} = \kappa_{2112} = 2C_{10}, \quad \kappa_{1122} = 0 \quad (19)$$

and, therefore, $\eta_2 = \lambda_1^{-2}$, $\eta_3 = 1$. Substitution of Eqn 19 into Eqns 8-11 yields the long-wave approximation (i.e. the asymptotic under the condition $\alpha_r \rightarrow 0$) for the characteristic equations for this particular model. As it was proved in the previous section, the solution of Eqn 8 will correspond to the results of the continuum theory. Substituting Eqn 19 into the characteristic equations derived in [4, 11] for the four considered modes of stability loss, four transcendental equations were deduced for the case of the model of piecewise-homogeneous medium. Then for each of the modes of stability loss we have a different characteristic equation in terms of

two variables λ_1 and α_r . For example, after some manipulations, the equations respectively for the 1st (shear) and for the 2nd (extension) modes become

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\lambda_1^{-2}(1+\lambda_1^4)^2[1-C_{10}^r(C_{10}^m)^{-1}]^2 \tanh \alpha_r \lambda_1^{-2} \tanh \alpha_m \lambda_1^{-2} - 4\lambda_1^2[1-C_{10}^r(C_{10}^m)^{-1}]^2 \tanh \alpha_r \tanh \alpha_m + \\
& + [2-(1+\lambda_1^4)C_{10}^r(C_{10}^m)^{-1}]^2 \tanh \alpha_r \lambda_1^{-2} \tanh \alpha_m + [1+\lambda_1^4-2C_{10}^r(C_{10}^m)^{-1}]^2 \tanh \alpha_r \tanh \alpha_m \lambda_1^{-2} + \\
& + (1-\lambda_1^4)^2 C_{10}^r(C_{10}^m)^{-1} (\tanh \alpha_r \tanh \alpha_r \lambda_1^{-2} + \tanh \alpha_m \tanh \alpha_m \lambda_1^{-2}) = 0 \quad (20)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\lambda_1^{-2}(1+\lambda_1^4)^2[1-C_{10}^r(C_{10}^m)^{-1}]^2 \tanh \alpha_r \lambda_1^{-2} \coth \alpha_m \lambda_1^{-2} - 4\lambda_1^2[1-C_{10}^r(C_{10}^m)^{-1}]^2 \tanh \alpha_r \coth \alpha_m + \\
& + [2-(1+\lambda_1^4)C_{10}^r(C_{10}^m)^{-1}]^2 \tanh \alpha_r \lambda_1^{-2} \coth \alpha_m + [1+\lambda_1^4-2C_{10}^r(C_{10}^m)^{-1}]^2 \tanh \alpha_r \coth \alpha_m \lambda_1^{-2} + \\
& + (1-\lambda_1^4)^2 C_{10}^r(C_{10}^m)^{-1} (\tanh \alpha_r \tanh \alpha_r \lambda_1^{-2} + \coth \alpha_m \coth \alpha_m \lambda_1^{-2}) = 0 \quad (21)
\end{aligned}$$

The elongation factor λ_1 is related to the value of strain ε_{11}^0 by Eqn 1 and is used here for convenience sake. As the result of solution, four dependences $\lambda_1^{(N)}(\alpha_r)$ are obtained, where $N = 1, 2, 3, 4$ is the number of mode. Critical value for the particular mode $\lambda_{cr}^{(N)}$ can be found as a maximum of the corresponding dependence. The maximal of these four values will be the critical elongation factor of internal instability for the considered laminated material determined by the most accurate approach (λ_{cr}). On the other hand, according to the previous section, the dependence $\lambda_1^{(1)}(\alpha_r)$, calculated for the 1st mode, gives results of the continuum theory $\varepsilon_{c.t.}$ if we put $\alpha_r \rightarrow 0$. Therefore, the accuracy of the continuum theory Λ (i.e. the ratio of the results obtained in the context of the most accurate approach and continuum theory expressed in percentage) will be

$$\Lambda = \frac{\lambda_{c.t.}}{\lambda_{cr}} \times 100\% = \frac{\lim_{\alpha_r \rightarrow 0} \lambda_1^{(1)}(\alpha_r)}{\max_N \lambda_{cr}^{(N)}} \times 100\% = \frac{\lim_{\alpha_r \rightarrow 0} \lambda_1^{(1)}(\alpha_r)}{\max_N \left(\max_{\alpha_r} \lambda_1^{(N)} \right)} \times 100\% \quad (22)$$

Numerical results

Values of the parameter Λ are given on Fig. 4 (for the interval of $1 < \Lambda < 30$) and on Fig. 5 (for the interval of $1 < \Lambda < 100$) in the form of dependences on the ratio of the material constants C_{10}^r/C_{10}^m . All eight curves correspond to different values of h_r/h_m . These dependences have the strongly non-linear character proving the importance of taking into account the materials' non-linearity. Another interesting revelation consists of the fact that the minimum values of all curves lie in the very narrow interval of the ratio of the material constants – approximately between $C_{10}^r/C_{10}^m = 3$ and $C_{10}^r/C_{10}^m = 4$. One can also see that the larger the ratio h_r/h_m , the higher is the accuracy of the continuum theory. It means that the increasing volume fraction of the stiffer layers has a strong impact on the implementation of the continuum theory making it more accurate. Typical values of λ_{cr} and corresponding α_r values are presented in Table II.

Following the general approach described in this paper the accuracy of the continuum theory as applied to composites with other properties of layers or other kinds of loads can be investigated. The final conclusion about whether to utilise the continuum theory can be made properly on the basis of comparison between the calculated in such a way accuracy and experimental data presented, for example, in [1, 11, 14, 15].

Table II: Typical values of λ_{cr}

C_{10}^r/C_{10}^m	h_r/h_m	λ_{cr}	α_r	C_{10}^r/C_{10}^m	h_r/h_m	λ_{cr}	α_r
10	0.175	0.8443	0.172	20	0.05	0.8946	0.274
16	0.150	0.8858	0.165	60	0.05	0.9483	0.210
25	0.125	0.9137	0.181	30	0.03	0.9189	0.250
48	0.100	0.9436	0.154	98	0.02	0.9623	0.184

Fig. 4: Values of parameter Λ plotted against C_{10}^r/C_{10}^m for different values of h_r/h_m

Fig. 5: Values of parameter Λ plotted against C_{10}^r/C_{10}^m for different values of h_r/h_m

REFERENCES

1. Guz, A.N., *Mechanics of Fracture of Composite Materials in Compression*, Naukova Dumka, Kiev, 1990 (In Russian)
2. Guz, A.N., *Fundamentals of the Three-Dimensional Theory of Stability of Deformable Bodies*, Springer-Verlag, Berlin Heidelberg, 1999
3. Rosen, B.W., “Mechanics of Composite Strengthening”, *Fiber Composite Materials*, American Society of Metals, Metals Park, Ch.3, 1965, pp. 37-75.
4. Guz, I.A., “Spatial Nonaxisymmetric Problems of the Theory of Stability of Laminar Highly Elastic Composite Materials”, *Soviet Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 25, No. 12, 1989, pp. 1080-1085.
5. Guz, I.A., “Internal Instability of Laminated Composites with a Metal Matrix”, *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, Vol. 26, No. 6, 1990, pp. 762-767.
6. Schultheisz, C. and Waas, A., “Compressive Failure of Composites, Parts I and II”, *Progress in Aerospace Science*, Vol. 32, No.1, 1996, pp. 1-78.
7. Soutis, C., “Failure of Notched CFRP Laminates Due to Fibre Microbuckling: A Topical Review”, *Journal of the Mechanical Behaviour of Materials*, Vol. 6, No. 4, 1996, pp. 309-330.
8. Brekhovskih, L.M., *Waves in Laminated Media*, Nauka, Moscow, 1979 (In Russian)
9. Rytov, S.M., “Acoustic Properties of Small-Scale-Laminated Medium”, *Acoustic Journal*, Vol. 2, No. 1, 1956, pp. 71-83. (In Russian)
10. Biot, M.A., *Mechanics of Incremental Deformations*, Wiley, New York, 1965
11. *Mechanics of Composite Materials and Constructive Elements* (Guz, A.N., Ed), Vol.1, Naukova Dumka, Kiev 1982 (In Russian)
12. Hill, R., “A General Theory of Uniqueness and Stability of Elastic-Plastic Solids”, *Journal of Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, Vol. 6, No. 3, 1958, pp. 236-249.
13. Treloar, L.R.G., “Large Elastic Deformations in Rubber-like Materials”, *Proceedings of IUTAM Colloquium*, Madrid, 1955, pp. 208-217.
14. Soutis, C., “Measurement of the Static Compressive Strength of Carbon Fibre/Epoxy Laminates”, *Composite Science and Technology*, Vol. 42, No. 4, 1991, pp. 373-392.
15. Soutis, C. and Turkmen, D., “Influence of Shear Properties and Fibre Imperfections on the Compressive Behaviour of CFRP Laminates”, *Applied Composite Materials*, Vol. 2, No. 6, 1995, pp. 327-342.